

Women Empowerment for Rural Development

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Abstract

The main objective of this study provides a strategy for women's empowerment for rural development. This book critically examines the transformation of this dialogue over the time and its implication in the improvement of the lives of rural men and women. The theoretical arguments for the necessity of introducing gender development strategies in order to improve the specific needs of rural women who are marginalized due to the magnitude of patriarchal dominations in the development administration has been field-tested in two sample locations where gender neutral and gender specific development project have been implemented in Sri Lanka. Empowerment can enable women to participate, as equal citizens, in the economic, political and social sustainable development of the rural communities. The findings outlined in this paper suggest that designed and implemented ways that meet rural women's diverse need, community participation processes can be important to facilitating social, technological, political and psychological empowerment in terms of rural development. The finding of this investigation can assist rural developers in the implementation of community development strategies based on women's empowerment.

Keywords: women empowerment, community development, gender equality, rural development, implication.

Introduction

The Gender Development Index (GDI) and Gender Empowerment Measure (GEM) put forward by United Nations Development Project (UNDP 1995) measure some aspects of women empowerment. The results of this review suggested a range of strategies that could enhance rural women's empowerment, including the use of agricultural cooperatives in this process. Organizational empowerment through agricultural cooperatives was identified as a significant approach to achieving the rural development. The GEM seeks to determine the degree to which women and men participate actively in economic, professional and political activities and take part in decision-making. But several writers critically examined GEM and GDI and pointed out the limitations of these measures to capture women empowerment at the individual level. Gender relations are the key to understand the Inequalities between men and women.

The planning process is effective and operational to this effort. Nevertheless, suppression of women is rooted in the very base of the Indian society. It is largely seen in traditions, in religious doctrines

and in all practices within the educational and legal systems. Women are systematically denied access to the resources that are available in their very society to fulfill any of their needs and responsibilities.

Means of Women Empowerment Education

Without proper and adequate education, women cannot become empowered individuals. They need to be encouraged to go for higher studies so that they can contribute significantly in the creation of a knowledge society

Communication Skills

Without developing skills for effective communication, women cannot make their voices heard. It is essential for them to communicate effectively to become successful. As leaders, they need to put across their points to the people so that a family, team or company can be effectively managed.

National Commission for Women

In January 1992, the Government set-up this statutory body with a specific mandate to study and monitor all matters relating to the constitutional and legal safeguards provided for women, review the existing legislation to suggest amendments wherever necessary, etc. Reservation for Women in Local Self -Government The 73rd Constitutional Amendment Acts passed in 1992 by Parliament ensure one-third of the total seats for women in all elected offices in local bodies whether in rural areas or urban areas.

National Mission for Empowerment of Women

With the specific objective of ensuring convergence and better coordination among the schemes, programmers of various Ministries, Departments, the Ministry launched the National Mission for Empowerment of Women (NMEW). The NMEW also looks at the inclusive development of women, including mapping vulnerabilities of women living in difficult circumstances, caste, different abilities, women headed households, ethnicity education, income minority status, religion, marital status, region, and so on as parameters.

Need for Participatory Initiatives for Women

Deep-rooted in ideologies of gender bias and discrimination like the confinement of women to the private domestic realm, restrictions on their mobility, poor access to health services, nutrition, education and employment, and exclusion from the public and political sphere continue to daunt women across the country. Other parameters that reflect the status and position of women in society are work participation rates, sex ratio in the age group of 0-6 years and gender based violence which remain heavily skewed against women.

- Social and Physical Infrastructure that are needed for development initiatives
- Enabling Legislations that brings gender equality
- Inclusiveness of all categories of vulnerable women through programmed initiatives
- Engendering National Policies and Programmers
- Mainstreaming gender through Gender Budgeting

The strategy would be to identify such workers and support their enterprises through setting up of common Facility centers to ensure all important services including technology and skill training, entrepreneurship training, market information, access to institutionalized Credit, power and other infrastructure and related facilities are readily provided. Special attention to the needs of vulnerable women, including the Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, BCs and Minorities, the strategies towards these groups must be crafted to ensure effective engendering.

Women Development Efforts

The First International Women's Conference held in Mexico city, wherein, a concern was expressed for developing a mechanism for providing women with access to credit as a means to encourage their integration in the development of their countries. In 1980, the second and mid-decade conference in Copenhagen adopted a detailed programme to ensure rural women to co-register the land title and equal access of credit, modern inputs and technology. The third conference in 1985 at Nairobi emphasized much on the initiative of NGOs in women's empowerment. The United Nations Women Decade also led the evolution of different theories from different feminist advocates and scholars, 'Women in Development (WID), Women and Development (WAD) and Gender and Development (GAD), and they were evolved at different times.

A Model of Rural Women's Empowerment

Drawing on Friedman's framework (Friedman, 1992) and the meanings and indicators of empowerment identified in the analysis, this illustrates the interrelationships between the four forms of empowerment that were identified, and summarizes the key features of each form of empowerment. Although these four forms of empowerment are discussed separately in this paper, there are clearly many interrelationships and overlaps between them.

The Types of Women's Empowerment

The major types of empowerment can be summarized into four groups.

Community Empowerment

Access to new and useful knowledge and awareness, developing new skills, abilities, confidence and competence, obtaining the friendship and support of other women, participating in various activities with other women.

Organizational Empowerment

New knowledge and awareness about new benefits of technology for rural development through rural tourism development or development of agriculture cooperatives.

Political empowerment: Influencing government policies and decisions that affect on rural communities, changing town-based people's beliefs, networking with people in government and industry and other women to discuss issues affecting rural women and rural communities.

Psychological Empowerment

Women's Empowerment through Self-Help Groups (SHGs)

A group usually consists of 15-20 members. Provision for small savings, lending small credit and other nonfinancial services are technically termed as micro-finance. Micro-finance is believed to alleviate poverty and empower women. Different approaches exist to explain the same. The basic idea of all those approaches is that increasing women's access to micro-finance will enable them to make greater contribution to household income. This improves the status of the women in household, and in turn, gives women the support to bring about wider changes including reduction in gender inequality in the community.

Conclusion

The main objective of this study provides a strategy for women's empowerment for rural development. Organizational empowerment through agricultural cooperatives was identified as a significant approach to achieving the rural development. Without developing skills for effective

communication, women cannot make their voices heard.. The access of women to key social services such as health and education is a critical determinant of the status of women and their ability to participate in making society a better place. Organizational empowerment through agricultural cooperatives is identified as a significant approach to achieving the rural development.

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